

Centre[4] Art and Research Services: Artists with an Interest in Research and Partnering

centre[4]
art + research

Abstract

This table is intended for those who identify somewhere within the following:

- Artists or arts organizations who are/who want to be partnering with academic researchers, and/or
- Artists who want to integrate aspects of research into their art practice or into their community arts practice (this could include program evaluation).

If you are considering working with Centre[4] Art and Research (C[4]), we can set up a meeting to hear a bit about your project or practice and to talk about the services that C[4] can provide. C[4] offers different levels of support/facilitation and an accompanying fee structure.

Administrative Details

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Service	Description	Fee
<p>Consultation A: Exploring and Clarifying the project</p>	<p>Consultation: C[4] will meet with you to hear about or think through, the role research and art play or could play in the project. We will work with you to identify or clarify your needs for this project. Here are some examples of questions we might ask:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What does research mean in the context of your project? ● What does art mean in the context of your project? ● What are you hoping engagement with research would do for/with your project? ● What are you hoping engagement with art would do for/with your project? <p>Connection: Connecting to McMaster researcher(s) who is/are working in the Artist's field of interest.</p> <p>C[4] will explain the hoped-for project and collaboration to a few artists who might be a good fit and where there seems promise on both sides. We will facilitate a meeting to talk through the potential collaboration.</p> <p>Connection might also include outreach via C[4], Centre[3] for Artistic + Social Practice, and McMaster University Community Research Platform (CRP) websites. C[4] and CRP staff may also provide connections via personal knowledge.</p>	<p>Consultation A is a free service. Along with the consultation, it also includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Direction to C[4] tools and resources, ● Relevant project examples, ● Referrals to funding sources, and ● Preliminary discussion of potential roles for C[4] in your project.
<p>After Consultation A, you may decide one of many paths to move forward. This could include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) not continuing with the project; b) continuing the project without support of C[4]; c) continuing the project with the initial support of C[4], such as that offered in Consultation B. 		

<p>Consultation B: What is the role of the artist in collaboration with the researcher?</p>	<p>Consultation: Part of the consultation involves figuring out what the role of the artist will be within a project. The following are a few options that we've identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Artist as lead – driving the direction of research ● Artist as co-investigator ● Artist as consultant – offer professional services as expert in their art practice and potentially theory ● Artist delivers arts programming as a way of generating data/stories/insight ● Artist involved in analysis of research data/ stories ● Artist involved in designing and creating knowledge exchange from research ● Artist provides knowledge sharing once research completed <p>(Please see our “Artist Role Frameworks” document for further discussion of these roles).</p>	<p>Consultation B, as well as all further consultations and work with Centre[4], will have a fee attached.</p> <p>The fee for services will be determined on a case-by-case basis.</p>
	<p>Examples: Providing relevant examples.</p> <p>Once we have clarified the nature of the research-arts partnership, C[4] is able provide some examples of art projects or artistic practices that have integrated research.</p> <p>C[4] will do our best to provide examples of projects that are either close to your field of research/art or that involve art/research in the way that you are envisioning/beginning to envision.</p> <p>C[4] will also provide access to publicly available research reports, websites, and more, as relevant.</p>	

	<p>Resources: Providing resources to support equitable partnerships (resources are free and available on the C[4] website).</p> <p>Here is a list of the written resources C[4] provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Examples of services in action ● Partnership agreement guidelines ● Arts output, process, and data sharing agreement ● Fee structure guideline ● Ethical considerations when engaging with the arts guideline ● Collaborative partnership checklist ● Sample workshop templates for arts involved research practices 	
<p>After Consultation B, you may decide to move forward with or without the support of C[4]. Your project might involve:</p> <p>a) continuing the project without support of C[4];</p> <p>b) continuing the project with C[4] continued facilitation as in Consultation C.</p>		
<p>Consultation C: Ongoing Consultation, Reflection, and Documentation process</p>	<p>Consultation: As the project as well as the relationships involved, shift and grow, C[4] may be able to provide ongoing consultation and reflection regarding partnerships. This includes checking in about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Roles and expectations, ● Budgets, ● Collaboration agreements, ● Ethical concerns and considerations, and ● Other needs/concerns that arise within the project. <p>Ongoing consultation also involves working with you to develop a plan for ongoing documentation of your project or practice.</p> <p>*see note regarding documentation process</p>	
	<p>Follow-Up: Reflecting on the process.</p> <p>Once your project is finished, C[4] will provide follow up/offer reflection on how the project went. Some questions we might ask are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How did this project go? 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• What's next?• What kind of support could you use more or less of?	
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*Something we've noticed in developing this work is that if documentation of a project is left until the end, it tends to land in the academic and/or less artistic realm. For example, academic articles and reports often provide much of the public facing information about a project. We want to encourage and support creative, ongoing processes of documentation, so that the *process* of the project can also be made visible and potentially celebrated!